

Current status of the Data and Analysis Preservation effort in the PHENIX experiment

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Abstract. The PHENIX experiment (*the Pioneering High Energy Nuclear Interaction eXperiment*) is the largest of the four experiments that have operated at the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC), taking data in 2000-2016. The PHENIX Collaboration remains active in completing a number of analyses of the data previously collected. In the past few years, substantial progress has been made in the area of Data and Analysis Preservation. We describe main aspects of this activity, platforms and tools utilized to achieve its goals, and briefly describe a concrete example of a recent important analysis being ported to the REANA platform for long term preservation.

1. Introduction

The PHENIX experiment at RHIC [1,2] took data in 2000-2016. It utilized a large, complex general purpose detector with a considerable physics reach and made crucial contributions to the search for Quark-Gluon Plasma (QGP) and study of its properties, as well as other research topics. Data and Analysis Preservation became a priority for the Collaboration in 2019[3], and since then, substantial progress has been made in this area. In the following, we describe various aspects and status of this work, and consider a specific case – the study of direct photon production in the $d+Au$ collisions – to illustrate our approach to Analysis Preservation.

2. Components of the Data and Analysis Preservation in PHENIX

2.1 Research Document Management

In the past few years the PHENIX Collaboration has consistently leveraged the Zenodo repository hosted at CERN[4], to preserve a variety of its research-related materials. A “Zenodo community” (an aggregation mechanism) for PHENIX was established on that platform, which allows efficient access to, and query of these materials under one umbrella. These materials include:

- Conference presentations and posters
- PhD theses
- Technical write ups
- Tutorials and other educational materials
- Select graphics and images
- A number of software items

We take advantage of the excellent metadata and search capabilities of Zenodo, and make a consistent effort to tag every added item with relevant metadata, including a curated list of keywords. This makes the materials reliably discoverable, e.g. it’s trivial to obtain a list of pertinent PHENIX documents related to a physics topic or a specific conference. More than 620 PHENIX items have been committed to Zenodo, including more than 150 PhD theses authored by the members of the Collaboration. Among the benefits of Zenodo is provision of Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), which is a major factor allowing the materials committed to this repository to remain reliably accessible in the long term.

2.2 The PHENIX Website

The public PHENIX website[5], rebuilt from scratch in 2019 in the process of consolidating and curating the previously existing, fragmented and partially obsolete web resources, is based on the static website generator technology, utilizing the Jekyll framework[6]. It serves as the hub of public information about PHENIX, such as

- Archived information about the PHENIX detector and its components
- A comprehensive run summary table covering sixteen years of PHENIX operation, compiled from a few sources
- Links to external repositories and web resources
- A catalog of conference presentations by PHENIX members, which includes *more than a hundred conferences and workshops* with PHENIX participation
- A comprehensive list of curated keywords, each linked to queries of the Zenodo repository (see Sec. 2.1). These include terms related to physics, detector technology, software and computing as well as conference tags for straightforward access to relevant PHENIX presentation materials
- Links to select tutorials, write ups and slides prepared for the annual PHENIX School events, and an assortment of technical information on the Analysis Preservation effort

The website is updated as needed, most often with references to new content developed by the Collaboration. Thanks to the chosen technology platform (Jekyll),

the website itself is virtually maintenance-free as it exists as a set of pre-compiled static files served by a Web Server. This also minimizes cybersecurity risks. Since a vast majority of the PHENIX materials have been committed to Zenodo (as explained above) there is very little storage-intensive content hosted on the website itself, which dramatically reduces its footprint and further simplifies maintenance.

2.3 HEPData

In the past years, the HEPData portal [7,8] hosted at CERN has become a *de facto* standard for preserving publication-related data such as data points used in plots, and data tables. Utilizing this resource allowed the PHENIX Collaboration to replace *ad hoc* pieces of data kept on a custom web server (which has since been decommissioned due to cybersecurity risks) with this state-of-the-art Web resource. The number of PHENIX items committed to HEPData prior to 2020 (23 items total) represented only a small fraction of the PHENIX publications. Thanks to the coordinated effort of the Collaboration to collect, format, review and commit both older and recent publication data, this number grew to 80 and a substantial number of items are in the pipeline. According to the updated Collaboration policy, preparation of the HEPData submission packages is now mandated for all new publications. In addition to the technical utility of this platform, it also provides a venue in which to engage undergraduate students in vital PHENIX data preparation activities, so it also plays an important educational role.

2.4 The Open Data portal

The CERN Open Data portal [9] is a powerful platform designed for the needs of Data and Analysis Preservation of the High-Energy and Nuclear Physics communities. It has been extensively used by CMS and other major experiments to meet a number of goals, including training, education and outreach[10]. This platform allows its users to create cohesive packages targeted for Analysis Preservation, which may include documentation, software (often in the form of software images), actual data samples and other supporting materials.

For a number of technical reasons, PHENIX cannot deploy full blown software images of its full software stack to open resources, so our effort materials for this portal so far has been limited to a package illustrating event selection in the Electromagnetic Calorimeter of the PHENIX detector. The package includes small samples of PHENIX data, documentation and basic portable software illustrating the event selection techniques. There are plans for development of more PHENIX materials for future hosting on this resource.

2.5 REANA

REANA is a platform developed at CERN[11] which aims to enable researchers to structure their analysis workflows and data in a way that makes their future reuse. The analysis is described in a structured manner by utilizing YAML files conforming to one of the available schemas, so as to capture sufficient information about the analysis assets, parameters and processes. The system features both CLI and Web user

interfaces, with the CLI option being more complete. The software environment is captured and preserved using Docker images, which can be stored either in a private registry or in a public cloud such as Docker Hub. The system can interface a number of clustering solutions to provide computing power necessary to perform computations. REANA has been used in PHENIX to capture and preserve some of its important analyses. More details about one such case are provided in the section below.

3. Preserving the analysis of direct γ and π^0 in $d+Au$ collisions in PHENIX

One of the important research items in PHENIX is the study of nuclear-modification factors characterizing particle production in various heavy-ion collision systems. For example, suppression of high p_T particle production in relativistic heavy ion collisions, like $Au+Au$ and $Pb+Pb$ has long been established and interpreted as a sign of formation of Quark-Gluon Plasma (QGP). Based on the data obtained in the 2000s, it was assumed that in small-on-large collisions ("small systems" like $p+Au$, $d+Au$ and so on) no QGP can be formed. Therefore, it was surprising when in the past decade experiments both at RHIC and LHC reported suppression in central $p+Au$, $d+Au$ collisions, and even more unexpectedly enhancement in peripheral ones[12].

One of the proposed methods of disentangling the various factors at play in these processes and explaining these observations is the analysis of the *ratio* of direct γ to π^0 production in different bins of event activity. The principal detector subsystem used in this study was the Electromagnetic Calorimeter[13]. Due to the importance of this study, a decision was made to make it available for further research, verification and refinement later on, and leverage REANA for this purpose.

As reported in [3], the PHENIX Collaboration and the computing facility at BNL worked together to create a fully functional software image that captures the PHENIX software stack. The image is used to run a number of workflows within REANA, corresponding to specific elements of the overall analysis. Currently, the analysis of direct γ and π^0 has five major components:

1. Extracting the yield of π^0 based on the detector data
2. Calculating corrections for this yield, accounting for various inefficiencies, using simulation
3. Extracting the yield of inclusive γ based on the detector data (the so-called "raw" distribution)
4. Subtraction of photons produced in hadron decays (e.g. π^0 , η , η' , ω), from this distribution (at the detector level) using decay simulations; this results in the single (direct) photon spectrum as measured by the detector
5. Using the single photon response matrix and other pertinent corrections, this spectrum is corrected to the final direct photon invariant yield

REANA has the capability of describing complex workflows in a single YAML file, using one of the available schemas, so technically it is possible to include all of the components into one large overarching workflow that REANA would execute. However, due to overall complexity and varying computing and data needs in each

component, it was decided to keep this analysis preserved as a set of well documented separate workflows. This way it is more accessible for the end user, and simplifies error recovery and experimentation.

The work to preserve this analysis is now in progress, with a large part of the component REANA workflows implemented and tested. Moderate modifications of the Docker image have been done to include certain data components for computational convenience.

4. Summary

In the past few years, the PHENIX Collaboration has continued its effort in the area of Data and Analysis Preservation. To that end, it successfully applied state-of-the-art solutions developed and maintained by the High Energy and Nuclear Physics communities such as HEPData, Open Data, Zenodo and REANA, as well as proven web development techniques suitable for durable, low-maintenance web presence.

A previously existing prototype of an analysis workflow (study of direct photons and π^0 in $d+Au$ collisions) has been substantially updated, with additional components included to reflect recent research, and to make it a more complete package for purposes of Analysis Preservation. This work is ongoing and more progress is expected.

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